

SOCIO-PHILOSOPHICAL ASPECTS OF THE ORIENTATION OF YOUNG PEOPLE TO ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTIVITY

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Abstract: *the article analyzes the importance of national and universal values in the orientation of youth in entrepreneurial activity in Uzbekistan and the importance of increasing the culture of entrepreneurship in youth scientifically-theoretically. It was seen as a contributing factor to the formation of entrepreneurial culture and skills in young people and increasing their economic situation. This view was interpreted as the formation of professional skills and culture in young people and, in turn, the manifestation of oneself as a socio-economic dependent national phenomenon.*

Keywords: *entrepreneurial activity, business philosophy, property, philosophical analysis, social relations, cultural sphere, axiological approach, pragmatism, civil society, market relations, liberalization.*

ЁШЛАРНИ ТАДБИРКОРЛИК ФАОЛИЯТИГА ЙЎНАЛТИРИШНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ-ФАЛСАФИЙ ЖИХАТЛАРИ

Аннотация: *Мақолада Ўзбекистонда ёшларни тадбиркорлик фаолиятига йўналтиришида миллий ва умуминсоний қадриятларнинг аҳамияти ва ёшларда тадбиркорлик маданиятини оширишнинг аҳамияти илмий-назарий жиҳатдан таҳлил қилинган. Ёшларда тадбиркорлик маданияти ва кўникмаларни шакллантириши ҳамда иқтисодий аҳволини оширишига кўмаклашувчи омил сифатида кўрилди. Мазкур қараиш ёшларда касбий кўникма ва маданиятни шакллантириб, ўз навбатида ўз-ўзини ижтимоий-иқтисодий жиҳатдан боғлиқ бўлган миллий феномен сифатида намоён бўлиши изоҳланди.*

Калит сўзлар: *тадбиркорлик фаолияти, бизнес фалсафа, мулк, фалсафай таҳлил, ижтимоий муносабатлар, маданий соҳа, аксиологик ёндашув, прагматизм, фуқаролик жамияти, бозор муносабатлари, либераллаштириши.*

СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ ОРИЕНТАЦИИ МОЛОДЕЖИ НА ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСКУЮ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ

Аннотация: *в статье анализируется важность национальных и общечеловеческих ценностей в ориентации молодежи на предпринимательскую деятельность в Узбекистане и важность научно-теоретического повышения культуры предпринимательства у молодежи. Это рассматривалось как фактор, способствующий формированию предпринимательской культуры и навыков у молодежи и улучшению их экономического положения. Этот взгляд был истолкован как формирование профессиональных навыков и культуры у молодежи и, в свою очередь, проявление себя как социально-экономического зависимого национального феномена.*

Ключевые слова: *предпринимательская деятельность, философия бизнеса, собственность, философский анализ, социальные отношения, культурная сфера, аксиологический подход, прагматизм, гражданское общество, рыночные отношения, либерализация.*

INTRODUCTION

Organizational and legal work is underway in the country to support the aspirations of young people to entrepreneurship. At the suggestion of our President Sh.Mirziyoyev's Youth Union was established in Uzbekistan[1]. In order to further deepen and expand youth policy in the country, accelerate the solution of socio-economic problems of young people, expand opportunities for their involvement in public life, including entrepreneurship, family business, a youth agency has been created. It is of practical importance to further expand the activities of young people to ensure their active participation in the development of society, the development of innovative forms of entrepreneurship. Therefore, young people, forms of entrepreneurship of innovative content inherent in the information system, develop depending on priority features, factors. They consist of:

first of all, loyalty to the national mentality in youth, the manifestation of the characteristics inherent in it in youth entrepreneurial activity, especially in the process of their involvement in family business;

secondly, the nature of the development of society in youth entrepreneurship is reflected, including modernization based on integration, with the expansion of business activities;

thirdly, it is determined by the fact that young entrepreneurs effectively use the scientific and technical potential formed in society in their activities;

fourth, as a result of the effective use of modern information and communication technologies in business, including family business, the level of opportunities for young entrepreneurs to use material and spiritual values expands.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

At the new stage of development of Uzbekistan, the formation of an information and communication culture for entrepreneurial activity of young entrepreneurs of innovative content plays an important practical and theoretical role, since this process expands the possibility of effective activity in the family business. At the same time, it should be noted that the process of conducting small business and family entrepreneurship in Uzbek society is characterized by originality. In particular, the enthusiasm inherent in our national mentality of young entrepreneurs is manifested in the fact that they work effectively in the cause of their goal, are committed to spiritual and moral values. Our historical and cultural traditions are characterized by the fact that young entrepreneurs believe in their personal capabilities, launch their intellectual potential for the implementation of entrepreneurship, in some cases are not afraid to take risks, realize the need to regularly improve their skills in order to use modern innovations in their activities.

This process, in turn, is associated with potential, innovative content and entrepreneurial activity for the future of New Uzbekistan, characteristic of the youth of Uzbekistan, irrigated by the essence of creation. It is also reflected in the activities aimed at ensuring the development of family business in our country in the current period. An important feature of the work of family business owners is due to the fact that during the activities carried out in it, the need to increase the personal responsibility of each entrepreneur for the work being carried out plays an important role. The deepening process of relations of the market economy in the country, in some cases based on risk, requires the adoption of special decisions on unexpectedly emerging problems.

Such a process requires each entrepreneur to find markets in which the sale of quality goods is intended, to strive for constant activity there, to some extent to receive dividends, to form immunity to external influences that change at a regular pace. The heads of business entities, in

some cases, create the need for each entrepreneur to personally enter into interaction with other economic systems, their leaders.

In the activities of young entrepreneurs, there is a state of special attention to cultural characteristics, which give an important place to a particular creative activity. Such an attitude, in turn, increases the competitiveness of goods, reduces external influences to a certain extent. Also, young entrepreneurs, based on their mental characteristics, strive to achieve a high reputation during their activities, show personal culture among their partners, qualities of responsibility in relationships. It should be noted that as a result of the rapid development of society, the trends in the innovative development of our country, the deepening of liberal-democratic reforms, the activities of young entrepreneurs, important aspects of our national culture and mentality are clearly manifested, this process, in turn, is the basis for the international recognition of the work of business entities.

For the activities of young entrepreneurs, especially in the activities of family entrepreneurs, the process of intensification in society is becoming more and more important, as the state of Uzbekistan goes deeper into the process of globalization. The positive changes taking place in such conditions are seen in the social life of young entrepreneurs, in the interconnection of innovation and traditional relations, in the conduct of activities aimed at an effective and perfect level, in the manifestation of the laws of the social system based on the principles of commonality and uniqueness. At the same time, the process of increasing the level of risk in the activities of young entrepreneurs is observed. This process is due to the fact that Uzbekistan is determined to build an open, democratic society, a serious effort has begun in the near future to gain a foothold among developed countries, business is gaining an increasingly innovative movement, the country's economy is gradually expanding its relations with the world community.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the development of the socio-economic fronts of our country, processes characteristic of globalization are taking place. Such a social situation is reflected in all aspects of entrepreneurship, including family enterprises, individual entrepreneurship, as well as other forms of entrepreneurship.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoyev in his address to the Oliy Majlis, paying special attention to the further development of small business and family entrepreneurship, noted: "We are mobilizing all our opportunities for the broad development of entrepreneurship and the creation of new conditions for this area. Within the framework of the "every family is an entrepreneur" program, loans in the amount of 5.9 trillion soums have been allocated to families starting their own business. As a result of our reforms, 93 thousand new enterprises were created last year, which is almost 2 times more than in 2018"[2]. At the same time, it should be noted that there are cases when the newly created business entities, including members of the family business, are faced with bureaucratic, delinquent, administrative barriers that exist in society. Complete recovery from these situations, their elimination plays an important practical role in the conditions of the development of civil society. In such conditions, it is important to pay special attention to human capital, to improve its qualifications, spiritual, moral maturity, and is a process of socio-economic development of society.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the acceleration of the pace of social development is also, of course, affecting the family business, which began to manifest itself as an independent enterprise. The processes of modernization and innovation in society require business entities to adapt to the conditions and requirements, to develop creative approaches.

CONCLUSION

As a methodological basis of the family business process, which is gaining an innovative essence at the new stage of development, factors of synergistic attitude, openness, cooperation, self-development are of significant practical importance. The essence of this controversial, complex process sets the task of scientific observation of socio-philosophical aspects, the development of conclusions and proposals of practical importance. Especially in this process, it is necessary to take into account the fact that the objective characteristics of globalization correlate with the trends in the rapid development of society. A scientific and philosophical analysis of the parties of the entrepreneur's activities, related to the real content and purpose of business labor, is required.

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